

THE IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATION THROUGH LITERATURE: WHAT IS THE CONDITION OF CHILDREN'S LITERATURE APPRECIATION TEXTBOOKS IN INDONESIA?

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Abstrak

This study aims to determine the condition of poetry appreciation textbooks used in universities in Indonesia. This type of research is qualitative descriptive research. Data in the form of interviews with informants and the results of document analysis. The sources of this research data include (1) informants, namely lecturers who teach Indonesian Language and Literature courses in the Elementary School Teacher Education Study Program (PGSD) throughout the Special Region of Yogyakarta (UNY, UAD, USD, UST, and UPY); (2) Semester Learning Plan (RPS) used to teach children's literature material or appreciation of elementary school children's literature (SD). Data collection using the in-depth interview method with recording techniques, as well as listening methods with recording techniques and transcribing recordings with orthographic transcription. The methods and techniques of data analysis used are interactive model analysis techniques, namely data condensation, data display, and drawing and verifying conclusions. The results of surveys and exploratory studies at five universities in the Special Region of Yogyakarta (DIY). The result of the study is that the children's literature appreciation textbook used by the PGSD Study Program in the five universities has not linked philosophical meaning and educational value in the study of literary appreciation, children's literature appreciation, especially those sourced from *the Serat Sari Swara* manuscript by Ki Hajar Dewantara. Therefore, it is important to develop children's literature textbooks that contain philosophical meanings and educational values that can provide a deep understanding of the meaning and message implied in the poem to internalize the educational values contained in literary works.

Keywords: Textbook, Appreciation Of Children's Poetry, Philosophical Meaning, Educational Value.

INTRODUCTION

Textbooks are one of the sources of information that become learning modules for students (Grever & van der Vlies, 2017; Savickey, 2020). Textbooks are arranged according to the structure and order of certain areas of science. In some references, a textbook is defined as a book used in studying and exploring knowledge, technology, and art that contains the presentation of subject matter according to the topic being studied. Therefore, a reference or teaching module can be said to be a textbook if it has fully described the material about the knowledge or knowledge of a discipline or subject needed by students. Thus the content is appropriate and used as a handbook for students in participating in learning activities in class.

Textbooks are books used to study objects of knowledge, science, technology, and art that contain the presentation of the principles of scientific work and related oblivion (Rifai, 2010, p. 1). Suryaman (2016, p. 2) that textbooks must meet the following criteria: (1) have a clear and up-to-date perspective and applicative, (2) have adequate content, namely a wealth of experience, varied, easy to read and able to arouse and

increase the interest of students, (3) have a systematic and gradual preparation method that pays attention to ease of understanding, sufficient explanation, the existence of illustrations, systematically organized, and direct disclosure, (4) has the possibility to present with methods and means that provide stimulation to students to be interested in reading it, (5) has content that is in-depth enough to be able to guide students to solve problems in a good field, (6) has evaluation tools that allow student competence in the field to be measured, and (7) has the potential to pique the interest of students who are interested in reading it. Learn more about the field. It can also be stated that textbooks enrich the textbooks used in schools (Trihartati, 2010, p. 17).

Textbooks can be one of the media or learning resources commonly used in teaching and learning activities. This is as stated by Sitepu (2014: 7) textbooks are used as one of the learning resources in the learning process and learning students. Information contained in textbooks should be able to help achieve competencies or learning objectives. Chen's research (Chen, 2013) also states that in Taiwan textbooks are considered as one of the important learning resources as well as teachers in supporting the success of learning activities. This is affirmed by Hutchinson & Torres (1994) who state that no learning situation achieves maximum results without using textbooks that are comprehensive and relevant to the material taught.

Four main reasons for the importance of textbooks in supporting teaching and learning activities: (1) many of the materials taught although not specifically designed for specific groups, but try to provide what learners need, (2) textbooks help make it easier for students to learn material independently related to the learning delivered by the teacher, (3) the availability of textbooks can help student learning activities independently when teachers cannot be present for (4) textbooks help teachers to develop basic competencies and improvise when teaching in the classroom (O'niell, 1982, p. 105). Given its importance, researchers want to conduct a study of *Serat Sari Swara* as an object of research that will be developed into a literary appreciation textbook containing philosophical meanings and ethical education values.

Based on preliminary studies, it can be said that literary appreciation textbooks containing philosophical meanings and ethical education values based on the teachings of Ki Hadjar Dewantara in *Serat Sari Swara* have never been carried out. Based on this, the development of poetry appreciation textbooks based on philosophical meaning and educational value is important to do. Moreover, the textbook includes the study of *Serat Sari Swara* by Ki Hadjar Dewantara as the object of study of children's poetry appreciation for students of the Elementary School Teacher Education study program. It aims to improve the ability to precision literary works and students' knowledge related to philosophical meanings and the value of ethical education contained in literary works, especially *Serat Sari Swara*.

Some important things to do this development research, among others, are as follows. (1) Researchers have not found a substantive study of KHD literary works, especially those entitled *Serat Sari Swara*, so researchers are intrigued to study and research them in order to popularize the teachings of KHD which are still in Javanese nationally or internationally in Indonesian textbooks and international articles. (2) *Serat Sari Swara* which is rich in teaching ethics (morals) and philosophical meanings can be a source in the development of literary textbooks based on philosophical meanings and educational values. So that in-depth research is needed to be able to reveal the meaning of philosophy and the value of ethics education contained in it can then be

developed into a literary appreciation textbook based on philosophical meaning and moral education based on the teachings of Ki Hadjar Dewantara; (3) literary appreciation as an appropriate means to explore, discover, appreciate and appreciate the literary works of Ki Hadjar Dewantara for the purpose of teaching and realizing the educational values and philosophical meanings contained in *Serat Sari Swara* in various contexts of life. (4) This textbook is expected to increase students' understanding of literary appreciation based on philosophical meaning and the value of ethical education in *Serat Sari Swara* by Ki Hadjar Dewantara.

Kennedy (1971) poetry is a rhythmic composition of words that express a behaviour, made to amaze and exhilarate and elicit an emotional response". This statement states that Poetry is a rhythmic arrangement of words that express behaviour (attitude), designed to provide surprise and delight and elicit emotional responses. This is in line with Waluyo (Suprpto et al., 2023; Waluyo, 2010) poetry is a form of literary work that expresses the thoughts and feelings of poets imaginatively and is composed by concentrating all the power of language by concentrating its physical structure and inner structure. Tirtawijaya (1982: 9) poetry is an implicit, vague expression with implied meaning, where words tend to have connotative meanings. Poetry appreciation is an award, an assessment of a literary work of poetry. Poetry appreciation is a literary work that expresses human life but the process of its creation through the power of imagination and creativity, which will be judged by literati (Nurgiyantoro, 2010; Pamungkas, Hastangka, Raharjo, et al., 2023; Pamungkas, Hastangka, Suprpto, et al., 2023).

In this regard, in both public and private universities in the Special Region of Yogyakarta (DIY) all lecturers use textbooks as their teaching references. Textbooks as learning resources or supporting books for students and lecturers in lectures that can facilitate the transfer of knowledge from lecturers to students. This certainly makes the study run smoothly in accordance with the learning objectives and learning outcomes according to the semester lecture plan (RPS). With the textbook, lecturers have no trouble delivering learning material. Dosen can provide advice to students looking for information related to the material to be discussed from various sources and textbooks if available. Students can more easily do the assignments given by lecturers using existing textbooks. Lecturers act as facilitators in lectures so that lectures can run smoothly and the quality of learning can be improved. Based on the background of the problem that has been described, the purpose of this study is to explore the condition of poetry appreciation textbooks used in Indonesian Language and Literature Learning lectures in universities throughout the province of the Special Region of Yogyakarta (DIY). The benefits of this research as a foundation for further research to be able to develop poetry appreciation textbooks containing philosophical meanings and educational values in *Serat Sari Swara* by Ki Hajar Dewantara.

METODE

Qualitative descriptive research is the main focus in this study (Creswell, 2014; Elo & Kyngäs, 2008; Merriam, 1998). Through this method, research seeks to understand and describe certain phenomena based on the data collected. One of the main data sources in this study came from interviews conducted with selected informants. Informants in this case are lecturers who teach Indonesian Language and Literature courses at various universities in the Special Region of Yogyakarta. Some of the universities that are the location of research include Yogyakarta State University

(UNY), Ahmad Dahlan University (UAD), Sanata Dharma University (USD), Sarjanawiyata Tamansiswa University (UST), and Yogyakarta Development University (UPY).

In addition to interviews with informants, data were also obtained from the analysis of Semester Learning Plans (RPS) related to teaching children's literature material or children's literature appreciation in elementary schools (SD). By examining RPS, researchers seek to understand how concepts and strategies for teaching children's literature are applied in the teaching and learning process. In the process of data collection, the in-depth interview method is the main method used. With recording techniques, informants can speak freely without being disturbed, ensuring the accuracy and authenticity of the information provided. Next, the listening method is applied with the recording technique. After the interview process is complete, the recordings will be transcribed with attention to orthographic transcription, ensuring that every word spoken by the informant is recorded well and clearly.

To process and analyze the data that has been collected, this study uses interactive model analysis techniques developed by Miles & Huberman (2014). There are three main steps in this technique, namely data condensation, data display, and drawing and verifying conclusions. Through these stages, researchers can ensure that the data obtained are processed systematically, objectively, and in-depth, so as to produce valid and reliable findings and conclusions.

RESULT

Findings: The Condition of College Poetry Appreciation Textbooks

Based on the results of surveys that have been carried out in the Special Region of Yogyakarta, namely Sarjana Wiyata Tamansiswa University, Yogyakarta State University, Ahmad Dahlan University, PGRI Yogyakarta University and Sanata Dharma University. The results of the exploratory study obtained the fact that there is no children's poetry appreciation textbook that specifically discusses the philosophical meaning and educational value of ethics contained in children's literary works, besides no one has developed a literary appreciation textbook (poetry) from *Serat Sari Swara* fruit by Ki Hadjar Dewantara.

1. The Condition of Children's Poetry Appreciation Textbooks at Universitas Sarjana Wiyata Tamansiswa Yogyakarta (UST)

An exploratory study at UST Yogyakarta was conducted in January 2022. The results of the exploratory study found that the children's literature appreciation textbooks used in learning Children's Literature were *Children's Literature in the Study of Structuralism, Sociology, Semiotics, to Creative Writing* by Heru Kurniawan. The results of exploratory/preliminary studies conducted through interviews with lecturers and students can be seen that there are still many students who do not have children's literature textbooks in Children's Literature Appreciation lectures. Based on the results of exploratory studies through interviews with lecturers and students regarding Children's Literature Appreciation textbooks, it shows that the textbooks used do not contain specifically about the study of children's poetry appreciation, especially those containing *Serat Sari Swara* by Ki Hadjar Dewantara. Therefore, based on interviews with lecturers who teach the Literary Appreciation course, it is necessary and important to develop a children's literature appreciation textbook based on the teachings of Ki Hadjar Dewantara.

Based on the analysis of documents that have been carried out in the textbook "Children's Literature in the Study of Structuralism, Sociology, Semiotics, to Creative Writing" by Heru Kurniawan, it can be stated that the material presented is complete and accompanied by examples. The results of the analysis of the content of multiculturalism conducted in the book "Children's Literature in the Study of Structuralism, Sociology, Semiotics, to Creative Writing" by Heru Kurniawan, show that the material of philosophical meaning and the value of ethics education based on *Serat Sari Swara* by Ki Hadjar Dewantara has not been discussed specifically. Given that *Sari Swara* by Ki Hadjar Dewantara is a source of local wisdom for learning literature for children, it is necessary to develop and package specifically in a literature appreciation textbook for PGSD students.

2. The Condition of Children's Poetry Appreciation Textbooks at Yogyakarta State University (UNY)

The results of the exploratory study can be seen in the textbook used in the Children's Literature Appreciation lecture in the PGSD–UNY Study Program Children's Literature. Introduction to Understanding the Children's World by Burhan Nurgiyantoro. The course specifically called Children's Literature or Literary Appreciation at PGSD UNY is not in the curriculum, but at UNY the material on literary appreciation is discussed in the Basic Concepts Course at Indonesian Elementary School. The special material that discusses literary appreciation in the course was about four meetings. The course is programmed in semester 1 with a weight of 3 theoretical credits which are compulsory. Related to modules or reference books used to teach literary appreciation specifically do not exist, there are still general references including Burhan Nugiantoro (Children's Literature: Introduction to Understanding Children's World), Sugihastuti (Children's Literature: Theory and Appreciation), Zulela (Indonesian Learning and Literary Appreciation in Elementary Schools).

Related to the content of philosophical meanings and the value of ethics education in the book, no one has specifically discussed philosophical meanings. Based on the results of exploratory studies that have been conducted through interviews with lecturers, it can be seen that there are still many students who do not have literature/poetry appreciation textbooks or children's literature in Children's Literature Appreciation lectures. Based on the results of exploratory studies of the Children's Literature Appreciation textbook used, there is already content about children's literature and the nature of children's poetry along with examples including Dolanan Song Poetry, Oral Story Tradition, Early Reading and Literacy but has not focused on children's literature appreciation material based on philosophical meaning and ethical education values from *Serat Sari Swara* by Ki Hadjar Dewantara. Given that the content of *Sari Swara* by Ki Hadjar Dewantara is a source of local wisdom for learning literature for children, it is necessary to develop and package specifically in a literature appreciation textbook for PGSD students. Data on textbooks used in PGSD-UNY are as follows.

The textbook for the Literary Appreciation (children) course used is "Children's Literature: Introduction to Understanding the Children's World" by Burhan Nurgiyantoro. The results of the analysis of the textbook document Children's Literature: Introduction to Understanding the World of Children by Burhan Nurgiyantoro, there is material consisting of eight chapters, namely: Chapter I on Children's Literature includes: The Nature of Children's Literature, Children's Literary

Genres, and Children's Literature Contributions. Chapter II Selection of Children's Literature Readings includes: Stages of Child Development and Reading Selection, Assessment of Children's Literature, and Where Children's Literature Readings are obtained. Chapter III includes: Dolanan Song Poetry, Oral Story Tradition, and Early Reading and Literacy. Chapter IV of Traditional Literature includes, On Traditional Literature and Types of Traditional Literature. Chapter V of Children's Fiction includes: The Nature of Children's Fiction, Elements of Children's Fiction, and Types of Children's Fiction. Chapter VI Children's Poetry includes: The Nature of Poetry, Elements of Poetry, and Types of Children's Poetry. Chapter VII Children's Nonfiction Reading includes: The Nature of Nonfiction and Types of Children's Nonfiction Reading. Chapter VIII of Children's Literature includes: The Nature of Comics, the Structure of Comics, and Types of Comics.

Based on the analysis of documents that have been carried out in the textbook, it can be stated that the material presented in the book is complete and accompanied by examples. The results of the analysis of the content of philosophical meaning and the value of ethical education carried out in the book, showed that it is known that the contents of children's literature, especially children's poetry, already exist and are accompanied by examples. However, in the book there is no material that specifically discusses the value of ethics education or the work of Ki Hadjar Dewantara that can be added to complement the study of children's literature appreciation from the work of the Father of National Education.

3. The Condition of Children's Poetry Appreciation Textbooks at Sanata Dharma University (USD)

The results of the exploratory study are known that the textbook used in the Literary Appreciation or Children's Literature lecture at PGSD – USD Yogyakarta Study Program is "Children's Literature Research Guidelines" by Riris K. Toha-Sarumpaet. Based on the results of exploratory studies conducted through interviews with lecturers and students, it can be seen that there are still many students who do not have textbooks for Literary Appreciation / Children's Literature lectures. The results of exploratory studies through interviews with PGSD USD lecturers and students obtained the following data. Elementary school Indonesian courses at USD include Children's Literature Appreciation, Indonesian skills, Indonesian Language Teaching Skills, and Dramatic Arts Education. However, for courses that are more related to literary appreciation, namely the Children's Literature Appreciation Course with a weight of 2 credits, it is programmed in even semesters (semester 6) with the nature of compulsory courses.

The reference book used for the Children's Literature Appreciation lecture uses books from Burhan Nurgiantoro (Children's Literature: Introduction to Children's World Understanding), Chartlot Hart books from Ohaiyo University, and uses a learning module developed by the lecturer himself entitled Appreciation of Indonesian Children's Literature. The module developed contains philosophical values such as ontology, epistemology, and axiology and also about the science of pedagogy of personality development, and emotional development of children. Emotional intelligence. However, based on the results of interviews with informants (PGSD USD lecturers) in the reference books used, none of them contain the philosophical meaning and value of ethical education from Ki Hadjar Dewantara, and according to

him, if there is a literary appreciation reference book that contains this, it is very good what else is sourced or developed from the teachings of Ki Hadjar Dewantara.

Furthermore, based on interview data, does learning literary appreciation have to contain philosophical meanings and ethical education values developed from the concept of Ki Hadjar Dewantara teachings? The answer or response from the informant (Pak Damai / UPY PGSD Lecturer) stated that he thought it was very necessary and he was very happy if there was such a book. He added that in the book Ki Hadjar there is the concept of neng-ning nung-nang, in the concept actually Ki Hadjar also applies the concept of education delivered by Montesory.

Incidentally, I am also interested in the Montesori method and PGSD USD also has a Montesori laboratory. I also think that in Indonesia since long ago following the philosophy of pedagogy education Ki Hadjar, surely Indonesia has advanced, because since a long time ago Ki Hadjar the concept of education has been constructivist. So he thinks it is very useful if literature can take part in reviewing and developing the work of Ki Hadjar.

The children's literature textbook used is the Children's Literature Research Guidelines by Riris K. Toha-Sarumpaet. The results of the document analysis in the form of a textbook "Children's Literature Research Guidelines" by Riris K. Toha-Sarumpaet contained a discussion of five chapters including Chapter I of the World of Children's Literature which consists of subchapters: What is Literature?, What is Children's Literature?, What and Who are Children?, Developmental Psychology, Brief History of Children's Literature, and Children's Literature and Children's World.

Chapter II Variety of Children's Literature, consists of subchapters: Early Childhood Reading, Traditional Stories, Rhymes, Fantasy, Realistic Stories, Biography, Historical Fiction, Nonfiction/Information Books, and Drama. Chapter III Examines Children's Literature: Several Approaches, consisting of subchapters: formalist approach / New Criticism, Historical / Historical approach, Reader-Response approach or transaction approach, psychoanalytic approach, and feminist approach. Chapter IV Researching Children's Literature: Theoretical, Technical, and Undoubtedly consists of subchapters: Some Thoughtful Prints in Researching Children's Literature, Children's Literature Researchers, Stages of Children's Literature Research, and Concrete Examples: Educational Institutions, Research Institutes. Chapter V examines children's literature: examples of research. And there are attachments of examples of children's literature works in the form of prose, poetry, and drama.

Based on the analysis of documents that have been carried out in the textbook "Children's Literature Research Guidelines" by Riris K. Toha-Sarumpaet, it can be stated that the material presented is complete and accompanied by examples. The results of the analysis of the content of multiculturalism conducted in the book "Children's Literature Research Guidelines" by Riris K. Toha-Sarumpaet, show that the textbook has completely discussed the nature of children's literature, the development of child psychology, the methods and practices of research on children's literature.

However, the book does not discuss the work of Ki Hadjar Dewantara in the field of literature, namely *Serat Sari Swara* which can be used as a source or reference to be researched and developed into a reference (textbook) in literature appreciation lectures and children's literature.

4. The Condition of Children's Poetry Appreciation Textbooks at PGRI University Yogyakarta (UPY)

The results of the exploratory study that has been carried out show that the children's literature textbook used in Literary Appreciation lectures or Children's Literature in the UPY PGSD Study Program is "Children's Literature. Study of Themes, Messages, and Techniques for Delivering Children's Stories Published by Newspapers" by Hasanuddin WS. Based on the results of exploratory studies conducted through interviews with lecturers and students, it is known that only a few students have textbooks related to Satra Appreciation and Children's Literature courses. Students mostly take online references from the internet both from scientific journals and blogs. The results of exploratory studies show that the textbooks used already contain a lot of character education or ethical values, but the textbooks used have not discussed much about the philosophical meaning of a literary work and moreover, there has been no study on how *Serat Sari Swara* by Ki Hadjar Dewantara can be a teaching material for literary appreciation and children's literature. Data on textbooks used in PGSD-UPY are as follows.

The children's literature textbook used is Children's Literature. Study of Themes, Messages, and Techniques for Delivering Children's Stories Published by Hasanuddin WS. The results of the document analysis are in the form of a textbook "Children's Literature. Study of Themes, Messages, and Techniques for Delivering Children's Stories Published by Hasanuddin WS, there is material consisting of five chapters, namely: Chapter I of Children's Literature which includes: Introduction, Characteristics of Children's Literature, Variety of Children's Literature, Fairy Tales and Grandmother's Stories Before Bedtime: Introduction to the Nature of Literature, and Closing.

Chapter II Children's Literature Readings and Study Approaches which include: Introduction, Children's Literature Readings, Children's Stories in Newspapers, Children's Literature Study Approaches, Character Education Values, and Children's Stories that are Used as Objects of Study. Chapter III Themes and Messages of Children's Literature Texts in Children's Stories which Include Various Themes and Messages of Stories Associated with Values, Education, Character, and Techniques for Delivering Messages or Messages of Goodness. Chapter IV Character Education Values in Children's Literature Texts on Children's Stories Covering Different Types of Character Education Values. Chapter V Content and Techniques for Delivering Children's Story Puzzles Published by Kompas Daily.

Based on the analysis of documents that have been carried out on the textbook "Children's Literature. Study of Themes, Mandates and Techniques for Delivering Children's Stories Published by Hasanuddin WS, it can be stated that the material presented is complete and accompanied by examples. The results of the analysis of the content of multiculturalism are carried out in the book "Children's Literature.

The study of Themes, Mandates and Techniques for Delivering Children's Stories Published by Hasanuddin WS, shows that there is no chapter that specifically discusses the philosophical meaning in a literary work and there is also no discussion about the work of Ki Hadjar Dewantara as a form of literary appreciation from the Father of National Education for the creation of his literary work (*Serat Sari Swara*).

5. The Condition of Children's Poetry Appreciation Textbooks at Universitas Ahmad Dahlan (UAD)

The results of the preliminary study that has been carried out show that the children's literature textbooks used in learning Children's Literature in the PGSD-UAD Yogyakarta Study Program are *Teaching Literature Activity-Based Children's Literature Teaching Techniques* by Taufik Ampera; "*Understanding Poetry from Appreciation to Study*" by Imelda Olivia W; and textbook "*Poetry Writing Techniques*" by Sigid Mangun Wardoyo.

Based on the results of exploratory studies conducted through interviews with lecturers, it can be seen that only a few students have literature appreciation textbooks or children's literature in Children's Literature Appreciation lectures. Based on the results of document analysis from textbooks used for lectures, it was found that the textbook data used had not focused on children's literature appreciation materials that contained philosophical meanings and ethical education values, especially those based/sourced from *Serat Sari Swara* by Ki Hadjar Dewantara.

The analysis of the textbook document "*Understanding Poetry from Appreciation to Study*" by Imelda Olivia W, is good because in the book there is material consisting of six chapters, namely: an overview of poetry appreciation; the nature of poetry; regarding the study of poetry; approaches and theories; writing and grading poetry; application of appreciation and study of poetry.

Each chapter has definitions, and examples, and is equipped with exercises and discussions. The goal is to make it easier for readers to know the purpose of the chapter. The book "*Understanding Poetry from Appreciation to Study*" is not based on character education, the presentation contained in the book is still in the form of general exposure according to existing explanations.

Analysis of documents in the form of a textbook "*Poetry Writing Techniques*" by Sigid Mangun Wardoyo, shows that the book is complete by focusing on seven chapters, namely: (1) the benefits of writing; (2) prerequisites for writing skills; (3) the notion of poetry; (4) the constituent elements of poetry; (5) poetry writing techniques; (6) creative process; and (7) publication of the work. The textbook is clearly presented in scientific language so as to make it easier for readers to understand the contents of the book. The book "*Poetry Writing Techniques*" describes complete material from understanding poetry to the publication of works, but the material presented has not been based on character education.

Based on the analysis of documents that have been carried out in the book "*Teaching Literature, Activity-Based Children's Literature Teaching Techniques*" by Taufik Ampera, "*Understanding Poetry from Appreciation to Study*" by Imelda Olivia W and the textbook "*Poetry Writing Techniques*" by Sigid Mangun Wardoyo, it can be stated that the results of document analysis that the material presented in the book is complete and accompanied by examples.

However, these books have not had a specific discussion about the appreciation of children's poetry and have not contained a study of the philosophical meaning and value of ethics education. Given that *Sari Swara* by Ki Hadjar Dewantara is a source of local wisdom for learning literature for children, it is necessary to develop and package specifically in a literature appreciation textbook for PGSD students.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the analysis above, it shows that some lecturers already have literary appreciation textbooks that are used in lectures. There are literary appreciation textbooks that have character education but some do not. However, as far as researchers can see, the literary appreciation textbooks used in lectures have not been published/based on philosophical meanings and character education values from *Serat Sari Swara* by Ki Hadjar Dewantara. Therefore, this research is an exploratory study stage in the context of developing children's literature appreciation textbooks containing philosophical meanings and character education values taken from the source of *Serat Sari Swara* by Ki Hadjar Dewantara. The importance of developing children's literature appreciation textbooks is also supported by several previous relevant studies as follows.

The cause of the failure to teach literary appreciation in elementary schools is the absence of guidelines or basis for teaching literature in schools and the decline in the ability of literary appreciation in students. This is also due to the lack of books or teaching materials for children's literary appreciation which are guidelines for teaching literary appreciation at the elementary school level. In addition, many teachers have difficulty in learning literature due to a lack of knowledge, abilities, and skills in appreciating literature (Saefuddin, 2022). Furthermore, he also said that literature learning is expected to be a medium for ethics education, moral education, or character education. This is very appropriate and supports the purpose of this research, namely the development of literary appreciation textbooks containing philosophical meanings and the value of character/ethics education.

Character education through textbooks is very important. Hafizah et al (2022) suggest that the implementation of character growth in elementary school children through children's literature can be done through three things, namely learning subjects, teaching materials, and learning strategies. Children's literature teaching materials that will be taught to children must contain elements of character education. This shows how important the analysis of the needs and conditions of the textbook to be developed must be in accordance with the learning and character growth of students. The development of Literary Appreciation textbooks that are more applicable, representative, and in accordance with the background and needs of students can improve the quality of learning literary appreciation (Ridwan & Hamsia, 2019). The stages of textbook development carried out by Ridwan & Hamsia include: *define, design, and development*. For this reason, Gunansyah (2015) stated that children's literature teaching materials developed are based on local cultural excellence with a moral cultivation orientation. This local culture is a very valuable relic and a reflection of the nation's character. Thus, it is hoped that local culture-based children's literature can be a means of cultural inheritance to the nation's next generation (Gunansyah, 2015).

For this, it can be seen that literature has a strategic role in educating children's characters. Literature, especially children's literature, is an effective medium in instilling moral values and expected character. In fact, various studies show that literary appreciation can be an effective means of ethics education. However, it is ironic when in practice, the teaching of literary appreciation in elementary schools experiences many obstacles. One of them is the absence of adequate teaching materials, as described above. Not only that, the teacher's ability to appreciate

literature is also one of the contributing factors. Therefore, the development of children's literature appreciation textbooks that explore the values of *Serat Sari Swara* by Ki Hadjar Dewantara is an initiative that deserves appreciation. Considering that Ki Hadjar Dewantara himself is known as a national education figure who prioritizes the noble values of the nation's culture in his education.

The importance of character education through children's literature was also emphasized by Hafizah et al. by mentioning three crucial components, namely learning subjects, teaching materials, and learning strategies. Therefore, an in-depth analysis of the needs and conditions of the textbook to be developed is crucial. Not only that, aspects of local wisdom must also be instilled in children's literature teaching materials, considering the importance of local cultural values as the foundation of the nation's character. In this context, the steps taken by Ridlwan and Hamsia in the development of textbooks are very relevant by including the stages of definition, design, and development. They emphasize the importance of textbooks that are applicable, representative, and appropriate to student needs.

From this, we can see that the emphasis on local culture, as suggested by Gunansyah, becomes very important. Children's literature based on local wisdom not only functions as a means of character education but also as a means of cultural inheritance. This is a strategic step to ensure that the nation's next generation not only has good character but also has a sense of pride and love for their own culture. Thus, the development of children's literature appreciation textbooks with philosophical content and character education values based on *Serat Sari Swara*, coupled with the use of local wisdom, is a concrete effort in facing the challenges of character education in the current era. This is in line with the objectives of national education which prioritizes the formation of a strong national character and noble character.

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis that has been done, it was revealed that although a number of lecturers have used literary appreciation textbooks in lectures, these books do not fully contain the philosophical meaning and character education values of *Serat Sari Swara* by Ki Hadjar Dewantara. One of the main challenges in teaching literary appreciation at the elementary level is the lack of appropriate teaching materials and teacher barriers to understanding and appreciating literature. Children's literature, especially based on local wisdom, has been recognized as an effective medium for instilling moral values and character. However, its teaching practices are often hampered by the lack of adequate teaching materials and the limited ability of teachers. Ki Hadjar Dewantara, as a national education figure, emphasized the importance of the noble values of the nation's culture in education, and therefore, integrating his works into teaching materials became essential.

Given the importance of character education through children's literature and the challenges faced, it is advisable for educational institutions and related stakeholders to collaborate in the development of children's literature appreciation textbooks that contain philosophical meanings and character education values, especially by integrating works such as *Serat Sari Swara*. In addition, it is also important to increase the capacity of teachers to appreciate literature so that they can teach effectively. Therefore, the instillation of local wisdom values in education must be strengthened to ensure that the next generation has a sense of pride and love for their own culture.

Character education through children's literature is considered very crucial in the formation of values in the younger generation. In facing various challenges in applying it, cooperation between educational institutions and various related parties is needed in creating quality children's literature textbooks. By integrating works such as *Serat Sari Swara* and improving teachers' abilities in literature, it is hoped that children can understand and apply the values of local wisdom in their lives.

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